

Project BioCombs4Nanofibers

D4.3 Cells first findings

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1. Goals and Detailed Description

D4.3 is a public scientific report on first findings of interaction between cells and nanostructures by partner **FORTH** and **INFPLR**. It will be published on the **BioCombs4Nanofibers** web-site as well as on the Zenodo open data depository. According the deliverable D5.2 Data Management Plan (DMP) - interim, it contains, among others, images of the structures before cell culture and images (confocal, optical, epifluorescence and SEM microscopes) by **FORTH** and in vitro studies on the interaction of the technical surfaces with specific cell lines by **INFPLR**.

The current deliverable reflects on the effort and results achieved in the framework of the Task 4.2 'Fibers on structures' that involves the processing of large area LIPSS samples, providing electrospun fibers for tests (e.g., adhesion test, wetting tests), and coating of samples with artificial nanostructures, nanofiber compounds.

The goals and results of this work could be summarized as follows:

A) Assessment of the adhesion and proliferation of cells on the micro-structured surfaces created using LIPSS.

LIPSS formation provides the possibility of generating numerous and unique surface biomimetic structures with multi-dimensional symmetry and complexity, exhibiting a broad range of sizes and spatial periodicities for a range of applications, including microfluidics, tribology, tissue engineering and advanced optics. The main technique for laser-based surface texturing is through a single step process with spatially concentrated focused laser beam (on time scales shorter than the electron-phonon relaxation time) in which an inhomogeneous energy deposition leads to self-assembly and LIPSS formation. The features of the induced periodic structures are related to the laser parameters while a series of multiscale phenomena such as energy absorption, excitation, relaxation phenomena, phase transitions and melt fluid

dynamics upon re-solidification determine the final relief ¹. The laser parameters that were used are depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Laser Microstructured stainless steel surfaces using two different laser parameters.

The two microstructured surfaces shown above have been used in order to determine if there are any observable differences concerning the proliferation and adhesion of cells between the two differently patterned substrates. These observations will also allow us to estimate their potential cytotoxicity.

The cells used for this assessment are murine bone marrow-derived mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) from C57BL/6 mice. These cells are multipotent, have the capacity for self-renewal without losing their multipotency and are able to differentiate into many types of cells, including adipocytes, osteocytes, chondrocytes, neuronal and myogenic cells. They have been cultured on the structured surfaces and prepared for SEM analysis.

For the **adhesion experiment**, the following process was followed:

First, stainless steel square surfaces, measuring 4cm x 4cm, were cleaned and sterilized by submersion in a 70% ethanol solution and UV sterilization for 20min. Then, MSCs were counted and 75×10^3 cells were seeded on each 4x4 square. This surface contained 4 smaller LIPSS treated areas (2 for each of the two wavelengths described in Figure 1), surrounded by flat, untreated surface. The cells were left to adhere and grow in low glucose DMEM (1mg/ml glucose) media supplemented with 10% FBS and antibiotics (penicillin/streptomycin) on the surface for 4 and 7 days, with media changes every 2 days. Once the cultures reached the predetermined timepoints, the cell fixation process was followed prior to SEM observation.

More specifically, the cells were washed twice with 0.1M sodium cacodylate buffer (SCB), fixed with glutaraldehyde (GDA) in SCB and dehydrated using graded ethanol solutions (from 30% to 100%). Finally, the samples were dried using increasing concentrations of HDMS (30%,

¹ <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/2008/2008.04275.pdf>

50%, 70% and 100%), before removing the final HDMS solution and leaving the samples to dry overnight in a chemical hood.

The adhesion and the alignment of the cultured cells were examined by SEM imaging. The samples were sputter coated with 10nm gold (Baltec CPD 030) prior to observation using scanning electron microscopy. SEM analysis was performed on a JEOL JSM-6390LV SEM with an acceleration voltage of 15 kV.

Figure 2: MSCs grown for 4 days on LIPSS structured surfaces created using $\lambda=1030\text{nm}$ (A) and $\lambda=515\text{nm}$ (B). The surrounding flat area is shown as a control (C).

Figure 3: MSCs grown for 7 days on LIPSS structured surfaces. Due to overgrowth, it was impossible to determine where the structured areas were.

As shown in Figure 2, the cells adhere equally well to all surfaces and seem to become more spreaded in the LIPSS structured areas. Surprisingly, the cells did not appear to align with the LIPSS ripples or assume any particular directionality due to the presence of the microstructured substrate. From Figure 3, we can also infer that the cells are able to proliferate without any apparent issues, as after 7 days in culture, the stainless steel surface was completely covered in cells and we were unable to determine where the structured areas were. Further experiments at different timepoints are already under way, with the aim to perform both SEM and confocal microscopy imaging analysis. Specific adhesion markers will be tested to determine how they interact with the different surfaces and to quantify any differences.

B) *In vitro* biocompatibility of the structures produced via 2PP

The *in vitro* biocompatibility of the structures produced via 2PP was tested using L929 mouse fibroblasts (as recommended by the ISO 10993- *Biological evaluation of medical devices*). Cells were seeded directly on the test surface and their viability and morphology were assessed.

Prior to the tests, the surfaces on which the structures were located were sterilized by exposure to ultraviolet light for one hour. Then the samples were placed in petri dishes and seeded with 50,000 L929 cells on each structure in 100 μ l MEM supplemented with 10% FBS. The petri dishes were left in the incubator for one hour for adhesion and then filled in with medium. Photos were taken at 1 and 24 hours after seeding (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Phase contrast microscopy images showing the morphology of fibroblasts on pillars (A, B) or lines (C, D) shaped structures one hour (A, C) and 24 hours (B, D) after seeding.

The figure shows cells that adhered very quickly with the expression of pseudopods in the early stages of adhesion, while then taking a specific, polygonal shape after 24 hours.

We can conclude that the material used is biocompatible and in current forms the architecture of the structures promotes a good adhesion. Other tests are in progress.

2. Evaluation of Goals and Resulting Actions

The main goal of the work performed in the context of this deliverable is to demonstrate whether laser-induced periodic nanostructures on artificial surfaces with similar size and geometry as the calamistrum surface can reduce the adhesion of the sticky nanofibrous capture wool of cribellate spiders. Thus, an assessment of the adhesion on artificial nanostructures with similar size and geometry to cribellate nanofibers was conducted.

The first findings show that both materials, as well as the different structures produced, are biocompatible and that cells are able to adhere well to them. The first experiments with MSCs have shown that the cells adhere to the microstructured LIPSS surfaces and are able to proliferate over the course of 7 days. Preliminary data from L929 cells grown on pillar and line shaped structures produced though 2PP also indicate good cell adhesion, with pseudopods being present within 1 hour after seeding and the cells taking a polygonal shape after 24 hours.

Future work

Cell experiments will be repeated at different timepoints in order to qualitatively and quantitatively determine the proliferation and adhesion in both cell lines (MSCs and L929). In this context, phase contrast, scanning electron and confocal microscopy will be utilised. For the quantification of cellular proliferation, the number of the adherent cells per mm² will be counted. The expression of specific adhesion markers (such as focal adhesion kinase, vinculin, paxillin) will also be investigated.

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